

Organ-on-a-chip, in silico models, and in vitro system - Animal testing Alternatives

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Abstract

Traditional research system primarily depends on data generated in research animals (laboratory animals and non-human primates). The contribution of research animals in several medical discoveries is worth notable and today also contribute a lot to the betterment of human and animal health. Research using animals usually involves many animals, time, money, and of course distress to research animals. At the same time, technological and scientific advancements in various disciplines and emerging healthcare problems like COVID-19 necessitated us to think of alternatives to accelerate research, improve the predictability of research outcomes, and follow the 3 R's principle of Russell and Burch. These alternative methods are commonly known as "New Approach Methods" (NAMs). It includes any technology, idea, methodology, invention, or combination thereof belonging to non-vertebrate origin helping to collect information on risks associated with chemicals, diseases, etc. for the betterment of human and animal life. The current article focuses on these New Approach Methods with their potential areas of application and their limitations.

Introduction

Research animals have helped human lives in many ways in relation to increasing life expectancy by the production of biologicals, understanding fundamental life processes, and disease pathogenesis, reducing human exposure to various risk factors, and much more. Their use favored the discovery as well as safety assessment of various novel modalities, treatments, and therapeutics, and is on the continuum of scale. Humans had used research animals on a large scale to solve various scientific problems and still rely on them for many aspects. The complex nature of scientific problems often employs many animals, time, resources, and great suffering to trial animals as in the drug development process. Despite their suffering,

they were used as a prime target in research as research involving human subjects is considered impractical and unethical. To prevent or reduce the suffering of these animals, animal lovers and environmentalists raised concerns across the globe. In addition, various legislation and initiatives were launched to limit animal research and ensure the proper treatment of animals. The US environmental protection agency (EPA) published a memorandum in 2019 advocating a reduction of animal use and funds by 30 % on mammalian studies by 2025, with a complete stop on the use of animals in studies by 2035. In the Indian context, the Government of India has formed a concise organogram for the overall monitoring of animal experimentation. The Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA) being the apex body supervises animal experiments via ethics committees in respective institutions known as Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC). Indian National Science Academy (INSA), New Delhi in addition has set ‘guidelines for care and use of animals in scientific research’ (Richmond, 2002). The requirement of many animals, time, resources, and suffering to the animals, and the predictability of animal data created a need to look for alternative methods commonly known as “New Approach Methods” (NAMs). The COVID-19 pandemic demands further refinement in the traditional ways of conducting research with the aim of an overall reduction in animal number, suffering, time, and resources required to achieve a scientific objective with equal or greater predictability than the animal models.

Scientific advancement in basic, applied, and allied sciences can help us to design, validate, and adopt tools considered to be NAMs. New Approach Methods” (NAMs) broadly refers to any techniques, tool, technology, or methodology or their combination of belonging to the nonvertebrate animal origin and helping to get information on the health risk of chemicals and their assessment. This can certainly help to advance the disease modelling process, toxicology, and pharmacology keeping in mind the 3R’s principle of replace, reduce, and refine the use of animals in biomedical research. Indian scientists also working on the same line to probe these emerging technologies to replace animals in research (Vaidyanathan, 2019).

Alternatives to Animal Testing

1. Human Organ on a chip: The organ-on-a-chip (OoC), is a microfluidic device system evolved through the admixture of biology with microtechnology. It contains live human cells, just mimicking human physiology, and is an exciting scientific and technological advancement to aid in drug development including personalized medicine, safety assessment, and in disease modelling (Bhatia and Ingber, 2014). Simply it is the network of microchannels mimicking in vivo vascular system and fulfilling the tissue needs. In this way, it is a mini version of an organ behaving like an in vivo organ in one or another way as elucidated and validated by scientists in human physiology and disease behavior (Bhatia and Ingber, 2014). The organ-on-a-chip may take any form from a basic single organ system to a much more interactive, and complex multi-organ system and body on a chip (FDA, 2022). Multi-organ system being complex allows the study of diffusible molecules and metabolites in a connected network in contrast to responses of a single organ observed in a single organ system. Several criteria must be considered while designing and using organ-on-a-chip the details of which were elaboratively explained by Bhatia and Inger, 2014.

Applications of Organ-on-a-chip: Assessment of efficacy and safety of chemicals both in preclinical and clinical settings, along with drug pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics (Tatosian and Shuler, 2009), disease modelling (Bliley et al., 2021), and radiation countermeasure development (FDA, 2022) are the predominant areas where organ-on-a-chip (OoC) are commercially utilized. Further, testing of biomaterials in the healthcare setting (Bai et al., 2021), probing of the cellular microenvironment (Titmarsh et al., 2016), and single organ functional studies (Beckwitt et al., 2018) are the other potential areas of application of organ-on-a-chip.

Limitations of Organ-on-a-chip: Engineering aspects related to design, manufacture, and at-end validation prior to its use are the drawbacks as the same was not standardized, necessitating more time and resources. Besides, organ-on-a-chip (OoC) provides information on end-point assays, hiding the spatiotemporal variation found in a biological system. Lastly, the data generated needs to be validated for

better understanding and prediction over a large scale (Leung et al., 2022).

Fig.1 Multi-organ Chip Design (Taken from Bhatia and Inger, 2014)

2. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (C. elegans): It is a nonharmful roundworm. It harbors distinct cells and tissues that function alike vertebrate organs and can be helpful in toxicological testing. It offers this opportunity on account of its easy management and short life-cycle of three days. Developmental and reproductive toxicity tests are currently conducted for reported toxic chemicals by FDA. FDA is currently working on the use of *C. elegans* to study the effect of chemicals on the nervous system, epigenetic changes, and oxidative stress studies.

Limitations: The absence of organs (like the liver, eyes, heart, lungs, and kidney), and the absence of an adaptive immune response complicates the results involving such a system. Besides, alteration in assay results on account of the development of adaptive response of alteration due to temperature, nutrient, or salt concentration change also has been reported (Hunt, 2017).

3. Expanded Decision Tree Software: A free tool software developed by FDA enables the categorization of chemicals into six different classes based on their relative toxicity potential. It envisages CDT tree (Cramer Decision Tree) for screening and assessing toxicity potential with the ultimate sorting of chemicals into three different classes (Cramer et al., 1978). Screening and classifying substances to varying toxicity potentials reduces human exposure to harmful chemicals and reduces animal use for safety assessment of chemicals.

Fig. 2. Infographic depicting *C. elegans* use in toxicological testing (taken from: <https://www.fda.gov/food/toxicology-research/c-elegans-model-toxicity-testing>)

Limitation of expanded decision tree software: Although the approach seems promising it is in its infancy stage (FDA, 2022).

4. In Vitro Cellular Systems: These involve 2D cultures, 3D organoids, and a Micro physiological system (MPS). We are well-versed with the use of 2D cultures in drug development and safety assessment. Even cell-based high throughput screening (HTS) of chemicals is carried out on 2-D cultures although they do not mimic the cellular properties of tissue. Nowadays, 3-D cultures known as organoids are gaining more interest as being more relevant to *in vivo* tissue for increased precision in drug discovery (Langhans, 2018). MPS is like an organ on a chip with the aim of replicating a specific organ described above under the heading of organ on a chip.

- Limitation of *in vitro* system: Although *in vitro* system can accelerate and predict research outcomes and toxicological assessment, it is not possible to exclusively construct or mimic *in vivo* system completely. Further, the extrapolation of *in vitro* system into *in vivo* system is challenging.

Fig. 3. Elements of an in vitro system in research and toxicity testing (Taken from: Ribeiro et al., 2019)

Conclusion

Research animals helped us in many landmark discoveries and saved countless human and animal lives. They sacrificed their lives for the betterment of humans. Considering the limitations of the traditional system of research using research animals, a shift was observed to an alternative approach known as “New Alternative Methods” (NAMs) across the globe within the regulatory and scientific community. These approaches offer great promise in relation to 3 R’s principle of Russell and Burch; can accelerate research with equal or greater predictability than animal studies. These are on the way to exploration and a road map for their maximal best utilization is being prepared by various regulatory and scientific bodies. Besides their potential, to summarize they cannot replace the use of research animals at all, as biological diversity offers great potential to solve any scientific question in its own way.

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